

FATIGUE DAMAGE EVOLUTION AND LIFE PREDICTION

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ABSTRACT

Cyclic damage development in polymer matrix composites may be modelled by a two stage process. The first stage involves transverse and shear cracking of the matrix which is particularly significant in cross and angle-ply laminates. Its development may be described using a two-parameter Weibull model. The damage rate continuously decreases until saturation is reached (Characteristic Damage State). This stage also occurs in unidirectional pultruded glass/epoxy rods due to early fracture of weak fibres. The second stage exhibits a stable, increasing rate of damage development resulting from longitudinal splitting, delamination and fibre fracture. This may be described by applying continuum damage mechanics. The summation of the two expressions results in a comprehensive description of the fatigue damage evolution process. Using this approach it is possible to predict complete damage accumulation and the fatigue life.

KEYWORDS: Composites; Fatigue; Life Prediction; Damage Development/Mechanisms.

1. INTRODUCTION

The main fatigue damage mechanisms in cross-ply laminates are matrix cracking, interfacial debonding, delamination and fibre breaking. These occur in two dominant stages [1]. The first consists of homogeneous non-interactive cracking which is restricted to individual plies. Damage develops at a decreasing rate due to the exhaustion of new damage sites and the slow growth of existing ones. The transition from the first to the second occurs when the Characteristic Damage State (CDS) is established and the

specimen exhibits a well-defined crack pattern. The second stage is characterized by the localization of damage in zones of increasing crack interaction. The proportion and amount of damage occurring during each stage depends upon the configuration of the laminate and the imposed stress level.

Similar behaviour has been observed in unidirectional pultruded glass/polyester rods [2] in which the large amount of damage observed during the first stage at high stress levels, e.g. $\sigma_{\max} = 0.88 \sigma_{TS}$ shown in Fig. 1, decreased as the stress level was reduced, shown in Fig.2 for $\sigma_{\max} = 0.51 \sigma_{TS}$. The term σ_{\max} denotes the maximum applied cyclic stress and σ_{TS} the static tensile strength. The form of the curve depicting damage evolution with number of cycles may be concave, convex, or a combination of the two, depending on the stress level and fibre configuration. However, damage evolution can be represented by a general curve similar to that given in Figs. 1 and 2. When the life fraction, $\bar{N}^{(1)}$, of the first stage is small, i.e. $\bar{N}^{(1)} \rightarrow 0$ a completely concave shape results and when $\bar{N}^{(1)} \rightarrow 1$ the curve will have a convex shape. A combination of the two occurs when $0 < \bar{N}^{(1)} < 1$. Under these conditions, although the curve is continuous, its first derivative is not monotonic. Nevertheless, the following conditions will be met during the first stage.

$$dD / d\bar{N} > 0 \quad (1)$$

and

$$d^2D / d\bar{N}^2 < 0 \quad (2)$$

where \bar{N} is the normalized number of cycles, N is the number of cycles and N_f is the number of cycles to failure.

For the second stage,

$$dD / d\bar{N} > 0 \quad (3)$$

and

$$dD^2 / d\bar{N}^2 > 0 \quad (4)$$

Hwang and Han [3] listed twenty cumulative damage models for fatigue. However, damage evolution in all these models is monotonic, indicating that the complete set of conditions expressed by equations (1) - (4) cannot be met.

For the general case, the total damage variable may be described by the sum of the accelerating ($d^2D / dN^2 > 0$) and decelerating ($dD^2 / dN^2 < 0$) components

FIGURE 1. Damage (equation 21) vs N/N_f at high cyclic stress in pultruded glass-polyester rod [2]

FIGURE 2. Damage (equation 21) vs N/N_f at lower cyclic stress in pultruded glass-polyester rod [2]

$$D = D^{(1)} + D^{(2)} \quad (5)$$

where $D^{(1)}$ is the decelerating part. For 90° and angle-ply laminates, it is mainly due to matrix cracking. $D^{(2)}$ is the accelerating part resulting from longitudinal cracking, delamination and fibre fracture. $D^{(1)}$ and $D^{(2)}$ may coexist throughout the whole fatigue life but each will control different stages. Generally $D^{(1)}$ is significant during the first stage and is constant in the second. Saturation of stage one damage corresponds to the Characteristic Damage State (CDS). On the other hand, $D^{(2)}$ is minimal in the first stage and becomes dominant in the second. By the summation of $D^{(1)}$ and $D^{(2)}$ all the conditions given in equations (1) - (4) can be met and at CDS

$$\frac{d^2 D^{(1)}}{dN^2} = \frac{d^2 D^{(2)}}{dN^2} \quad (6)$$

The present work deals with describing the damage accumulated at different stress levels in a composite and forms the basis for studies which will enable the service life to be predicted when the component is subjected to fatigue at multiple stress levels.

2. STAGE 1 - DECELERATING DAMAGE EVOLUTION

Investigations [4] on cross-ply laminates have shown that the first event of failure is the debonding of transverse fibres, which result in matrix cracking in the 90° degree plies. The accumulation of matrix cracks may be described by a two-parameter Weibull expression

$$F(N) = 1 - \exp \{ -(N/\alpha)^\beta \} \quad (7)$$

$F(N)$ is the cumulative probability function for matrix cracking which can be determined from experimental observations:

$$F(N) = n / n_c \quad (8)$$

where n is the number of cracks, n_c is the number of cracks at CDS, α is the scale parameter of the Weibull curve and β is the shape parameter of the Weibull curve.

Considering the work on graphite/epoxy cross-ply laminates by Daniel et al [5], the function given by equation (8) is shown in Fig. 3. The parameters α and β are determined by replottting function $F(N)$ in the Weibull probability form, given in Fig. 4. In this manner the probability for transverse cracking at various cyclic stress levels

FIGURE 3. Stage 1 crack data (equation 8) and described crack function (equation 7) vs N for $[0, 90]_s$ graphite-epoxy laminate [5]

FIGURE 4. Weibull probability curves. Stage 1 crack development (as shown in Figure 3) for $[0, 90]_s$ graphite-epoxy laminate [5]

for the $[0/90_2]_s$ graphite/epoxy laminate may be described graphically and these curves are included in Fig. 3, demonstrating good agreement with the experimental data. The parameters α and β are functions of stress level and for the experimental data cited in [5] they are expressed by

$$\alpha = 10^{14.9 + 24.1 (\sigma_{\max}/\sigma_{TS})} \quad (9)$$

$$\text{and } \beta = 0.7482 - 1.5394 (\sigma_{\max}/\sigma_{TS})^{1/2} + 8610 (\sigma_{\max}/\sigma_{TS}) \quad (10)$$

Differentiating equation (7), the probability density function can be written

$$f(N) = \beta \alpha^{-\beta} N^{\beta-1} \exp\{- (N/\alpha)^\beta\} \quad (11)$$

This equation accurately describes the rate of cracking with number of cycles for a cross-ply laminate when the corresponding values for the Weibull parameters are known. It shows that there is an initially high rate of cracking in the matrix and that this decreases rapidly with number of cycles.

The relation between crack density and longitudinal elastic modulus, which may be used to measure damage, has been analyzed by many authors using different approaches, such as the self-consistent model [6], the variation approach [7], the shear-lag model [8], and continuum damage mechanics [9]. The longitudinal component of the damage tensor can be expressed by the number of cracks as

$$D_{11} = \Psi_1(\bar{E}_{11}) = \Psi_2(n) \quad (12)$$

where \bar{E}_{11} is the longitudinal stiffness of the damaged material and Ψ_1 and Ψ_2 are functions. Applying continuum damage mechanics [9], the equation expressing the longitudinal damage tensor (D_{11} or $D^{(1)}$ in equation 5) in terms of crack density for cross-ply laminates takes the form:

$$D_{11} = kn t_c^2 / Lt \quad (13)$$

where L is the gauge length, t_p is the thickness of the damaged (cracked) plies, t is the thickness of the laminate and k is a constant.

Substituting equations (7), (8) into equation (13), yields:

$$D_{11} = D_c [1 - \exp\{- (N_F \bar{N}/\alpha)^\beta\}] \quad (14)$$

The damage at CDS is given by

$$D_c = kn_c t_D^2 / Lt \quad (15)$$

3. STAGE 2 - ACCELERATING DAMAGE EVOLUTION

Since damage evolution for the accelerating process involves the coalescence of micro-cracks and development of macro-cracks, the growth rate may be expressed by:

$$da / dN = A (\Delta K)^m \quad (16)$$

where a is the crack depth, A is a constant, ΔK is the cyclic stress intensity factor and m is an exponent. However, there is no clear definition of crack length and the crack tip stress intensity factor for the multi-damage mechanisms which take place. Considering the onset and growth of delaminations in a composite cycled at a constant strain amplitude, O'Brien [10] used the maximum strain energy release rate G_{\max} to replace ΔK in the Paris equation (16),

$$da / dN = C (G_{\max})^r \quad (17)$$

where C and r are material constants. Since multi-damage mechanisms occur during this stage, crack length is replaced by the more descriptive parameter for damage, D . This is an internal state variable which can be included in constitutive equations of elastic-plastic mechanics and measured by modulus change, cracked area and void density, etc. [11]. Accordingly, da/dN in equation (17) may be written as dD/dN and Y_{\max} , the counterpart of G_{\max} in damage mechanics, may be substituted. So equation (18) becomes

$$dD / dN = C (Y_{\max})^r \quad (18)$$

where Y_{\max} is the maximum value in a cycle of the damage strain energy release rate Y , proposed by Chaboche [12]. At constant stress, σ , and temperature, T , this may be expressed by

$$Y = 1/2 dW_e / dD \big|_{\sigma, T} \quad (19)$$

where the term dW_e is the increment of elastic strain energy density which is the product of the applied stress and the elastic strain increment,

$$dW_e = \sigma de \quad (20)$$

Damage may be quantified by dividing the apparent modulus of the damaged material, E , by the undamaged modulus, E , [11] as follows:

$$D = 1 - \bar{E}/E \quad (21)$$

or more generally [13],

$$D = 1 - (\bar{E}/E)^l \quad (22)$$

where l is a constant.

Substituting equations (20), (22) into equation (19), yields

$$Y = \sigma^2 / [2lE (1-D)^{1+l/l}] \quad (23)$$

Also, substituting equation (23) into equation (18), yields

$$dD/dN = \{\sigma_{\max} / B(1-D)\}^v (1-D)^{-w} \quad (24)$$

where B, v and w , are constants. Equation (24) is the differential form for the evolution of transgranular cracks during fatigue when the mean stress is 0 ($R = -1$), as proposed by Lemaître and Plumtree [14]. This equation can be written in the integral form

$$D = 1 - (1-\bar{N})^\gamma \quad (25)$$

where γ is a constant.

Equation (25) may be modified by introducing the coefficient D_a to account for the existence of prior damage and that the critical value of D at fracture ranges from 0.2 to 0.8 [15]. Hence for the second stage of damage in composites

$$D^{(2)} = D_a [1 - (1-\bar{N})^\gamma] \quad (26)$$

Substituting equations (14) and (26) into equation (5), the general form for damage evolution in a composite may then be written

$$D = D_c [1 - \exp \{- (N_f \bar{N}/\alpha)^\beta\}] + D_a [1 - (1-\bar{N})^\gamma] \quad (27)$$

4. VERIFICATION - FATIGUE OF PULTRUDED GLASS POLYESTER RODS

As in the case of cyclically loaded 90° and angle-ply laminates, a variety of microscopic

damage mechanisms, such as matrix cracking, fibre/matrix debonding, delamination, longitudinal cracking and fibre fracture, have been observed in pultruded glass/polyester rods by Jessen and Plumtree [2]. Initially, decelerating damage evolution occurred due to the early fracture of weak or damaged fibres and matrix cracking in resin rich areas, particularly where the fibres were misaligned. Consequently the material displayed stage 1 damage behaviour. With perfectly aligned fibres of uniform strength, this stage should be absent. In the example under consideration [2], however, it is acceptable to use the two-stage model to describe damage evolution. Fig. 1 gives the experimental data and described damage evolution curve for a stress level of $\sigma_{\max}/\sigma_{TS} = 0.88$ ($R = 0.05$). Fig. 2 is a similar plot for $\sigma_{\max}/\sigma_{TS} = 0.51$ ($R = 0.05$). The parameters α (15.17 for $\sigma_{\max}/\sigma_{TS} = 0.88$ and 11430 for $\sigma_{\max}/\sigma_{TS} = 0.51$), β (1.04 for $\sigma_{\max}/\sigma_{TS} = 0.88$ and 1.12 for $\sigma_{\max}/\sigma_{TS} = 0.51$), γ (0.23 for $\sigma_{\max}/\sigma_{TS} = 0.88$ and 0.22 for $\sigma_{\max}/\sigma_{TS} = 0.51$) in equation (27), were obtained by least squares fits. It is seen that the damage curve described by equation (27) is in very good agreement with the experimental data.

Based on Figs. 1 and 2, the life of two stress-level tests (high to low or low to high) may be predicted. For a high to low test, the specimen was first cycled at the stress level $\sigma_{\max}/\sigma_{TS} = 0.88$ for a life fraction $\bar{N} = 0.189$, then the stress was decreased to $\sigma_{\max}/\sigma_{TS} = 0.51$ until failure which occurred after a further 330587 cycles. Using the two stage damage model the predicted number of cycles was 431874. This is reasonable when the relatively large standard deviation for N_f at each stress level is considered. It should be noted that the predicted number of cycles using the linear damage rule was 564017, resulting in an error of 70.6% compared to 30.6% for the two stage damage model.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The accumulation of fatigue damage in a composite material may be described by a general model which includes decelerating and accelerating damage components. This two stage model accounts for the variety of damage mechanisms that develop throughout the life of the material and may be applied to predict the fatigue life of single and two-level stress tests.

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